

Supervisor Influence on Employee Psychological Safety

Qualitative Descriptive Study Protocol and Interview Instrument

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Abstract

This qualitative descriptive study protocol explores how federal government employees in Hawaii describe psychological safety and their supervisors' influence on it within the workplace. The protocol and associated instruments were developed to guide data collection, ensure methodological transparency, and support replication. The instrument includes a demographic questionnaire, open-ended written questionnaire, and semi-structured interview questions designed to elicit rich, descriptive data related to workplace psychological safety, supervisor influence, and employee engagement.

Keywords: qualitative, interview, protocols, questionnaire, psychological safety, descriptive

Appendix E.

Questionnaire/Interview Data Instruments

Demographic Questionnaire

This demographic questionnaire will be utilized to obtain key demographic information concerning the sample participants. This information will confirm that the sample participants meet criteria set by the researcher. The criteria collected includes age, gender, current position at your organization, years of working in current position, and number of years working for your current supervisor. The demographic questionnaire will be provided through the SurveyMonkey application link to the informed consent and study questionnaire included in the research flyer.

1. Age: 18-24, 25-34, 35-44, 45-54, 55-64, 65+
2. Gender: _____
3. Current position at your organization: _____
4. Years of working in current position: _____
5. Years working for current supervisor: 2-5, 6-10, 11-15, 16+

Sincerely,

Vernon Brown
Doctoral Student
Grand Canyon University

Open-Ended Questionnaire Protocol

The purpose of this qualitative descriptive study is to explore how federal government employees of Hawaii describe psychological safety and their supervisors' influence on psychological safety in the workplace.

Psychological safety is an important construct used in the study. The definition of this term is provided below:

Psychological safety is a shared belief that an organization is safe for employees to share ideas and fully express feelings without fear of rejection, punishment or retribution that affects well-being (Edmondson, 1999; Newman et al., 2017). The questions outlined in the open-ended questionnaire explore the perception one feels regarding the explained meaning of psychological safety and their supervisors' influence on their psychological safety.

1. Describe why psychological safety is important in the workplace. (RQ1)
2. Based on the provided definition of psychological safety, explain what aspect(s) of psychological safety is/are most important to you. (RQ1)
3. Tell me about your supervisor's commitment to the psychological safety of employees. (RQ2)
4. Describe your supervisor's communication skills and how it affects your workplace psychological well-being. (RQ2)
5. Describe a method of interaction your supervisor provides, or should provide, to allow you to freely communicate within the workplace. (RQ1, RQ2)
6. Describe a recent interaction you had with your supervisor and how it made you feel about your psychological safety in the workplace. (RQ2)
7. Describe your level of engagement and trust with your supervisor. (RQ2)
8. Describe how your coworkers react when you share concerns, ideas, or thoughts. (RQ1)
9. Describe how your supervisor reacts when you share concerns, ideas, or thoughts. (RQ1)
10. Describe how your upper-level leadership reacts when you share concerns, ideas, or thoughts. (RQ1)
11. Describe other ways that encourage you to feel safe and speak up in the workplace. (RQ1)

**** Qualification question for interview participation***

12. Are you willing to be interviewed? **Yes/No ***

The interview phase will further explore how you describe your supervisors' influence on psychological safety in your government organization. The data gathered in the interview phase may increase knowledge in the phenomenon of supervisor influence on psychological safety. The results will be used to develop a richer understanding to answer the research questions posed in this study. The interview would last approximately one hour. It could take place between May 2022 and August 2022. If interested, please provide your contact information below where you can be reached:

Email address

Phone Number (Optional)

Semi-Structured Interview Protocol

Interview Project: Supervisor Influence on Employee Psychological Safety in U.S. Federal

Government Organizations: A Qualitative Descriptive Study

Date of Interview: _____

Time of Interview: Begin: _____ End: _____

Interviewer: Vernon Brown

Participant Pseudonym: _____

In accordance with the interview script, the researcher will conduct the interview process in the following manner:

1. The researcher will thank the participant.
2. The researcher will review the purpose of the study.
3. The researcher reminds the participant of their rights, the confidentiality agreement, and destruction of data in the informed consent form.
4. The researcher will review the key term(s) and concept(s) provided for the study.

Psychological safety is an important construct used throughout the study and in the context of the interview questions. Psychological safety is a shared belief that an organization is safe for employees to share ideas and fully express feelings without fear of rejection, punishment or retribution that affects well-being (Edmondson, 1999; Newman et al., 2017). The questions outlined in the one-on-one interview explore the perception one feels regarding the explained meaning of psychological safety and their supervisors' influence on their psychological safety.

Associated terms used throughout the study are:

- a. **Employee Engagement.** The opposite of burnout, employee engagement refers to a positive, fulfilling, work-related state of mind towards work tasks.
- b. **Organizational Adaptability.** A derivative of organizational change, organizational adaptability is about setting expectations for the individual employee and the organization to adjust to the ever-changing environment and mobilizing followers to overcome challenges and improve the organization.

- c. **Organizational Culture.** A pattern of shared basic assumptions that an organization learns as it solves its problems of external adaptation and internal integration that has worked well; therefore, the organization teaches to new members the correct way it perceives, thinks, and feels in relation to those problems.
 - d. **Organizational Performance.** The collective performance of individual employees of an organization.
 - e. **Prosocial Motivation.** The desire to expend effort to benefit other people.
 - f. **Psychological Safety.** The extent to which employees feel comfort in taking interpersonal risks that are positive and free of embarrassment, shame, or ridicule.
 - g. **Psychosocial Safety Climate.** Consists of policies, practices, and procedures developed and implemented within an organization to ensure the protection of workers' psychological health and safety.
5. The researcher will review the logistics of the study (time and answering of questions).
 6. The researcher will ask for permission to audio record or video record the interview.
 7. The researcher will ask participants if they have any other questions before the interview begins.
 8. The researcher will begin the interview.

Interview Script

Thank you for taking the time to meet with me today. Are you currently in a private or secure location?

The purpose of this qualitative descriptive study is to explore how federal government employees of Hawaii describe psychological safety and their supervisors' influence on psychological safety in the workplace.

As a reminder, the Informed Consent Form that you agreed to indicated that your participation in this study is completely voluntary and you may stop your participation at any time without any consequences. You may skip questions without any penalty during the interview process. If you choose to withdraw, your data will not be used.

Participation and all responses are confidential unless disclosure is required by law. All data collected will be provided a unique pseudonym to protect your identity. Data collected during this interview will be password-protected on USB flash drives and stored for three years in a secure lockbox that only I have access to, unless the dissertation chair and committee, peer reviewer, Institutional Review Board, or College of Doctoral Studies representative request access. After three years, the electronic data stored on the flash drives will be erased.

Do you have any questions regarding the consent or the purpose of the study?

This interview will take approximately 60 minutes. There are no right or wrong answers to the questions you will be asked. Please answer to the best of your ability or recollection.

1. Do I have your permission to audio record (video record) this interview?
2. Do you have any other questions before we begin the interview?

Interview Questions

1. Describe your perception of your organization's psychological safety. (RQ1)
 - Probe 1 – What impact do you think your perception of psychological safety has on your work engagement?
2. Please describe how psychological safety is included within your organization policies. Please provide an example. (RQ1)
 - Probe 1 – How has your organization policy influenced your well-being, engagement, and productivity?
 - Probe 2 – What would you do if you could change your organization policies to further support psychological safety?
3. Describe how your perception of psychological safety influences your contribution to the organization, if any. (RQ1)
 - Probe 1 – You mentioned... could you tell me a little bit more about that please?
 - Probe 2 – What is the single most important thing you would focus on within your organization to change your perception?
4. Describe the ways you express your feedback, ideas, and concerns within your organization. (RQ1)
 - Probe 1 – Describe your official organization policy and process for submitting feedback, ideas, and concerns.
 - Probe 2 – What change would you like to make in your official organization policy for submitting feedback, ideas, and concerns?
5. Describe what you have experienced when trying to express your opinions or ideas within your workplace. (RQ1)
 - Probe 1 – Please describe your most vivid experience(s).
 - Probe 2 – Just to make sure that I fully understand the problem, could you give me an example of what you mean by...
 - Probe 3 – What would you do, if anything, to change the experience you felt when you expressed your opinions or ideas?
6. Please describe how psychological safety has impacted your sense of belonging or acceptance in the workplace, if any. (RQ1)
 - Probe 1 – Please describe how you feel when you share your personal characteristics or put forth an effort to be yourself.
 - Probe 2 – Please describe changes you may have made to your personal characteristics or actions to fit in and feel accepted in your workplace.
7. Please describe how psychological safety affects your motivation to learn and expand your professional knowledge within the workplace. (RQ1).

- Probe 1 – How has your workplace psychological safety affected your desire to learn new things relevant to your work?
- Probe 2 – How has your workplace psychological safety affected your involvement in new projects in your workplace?
8. Please describe any changes you have experienced in the psychological safety of your current organization since you first started your employment with them. (RQ1)
- Probe 1 – What has been the cause of the changes you have experienced?
- Probe 2 – What changes have created the most impact? Why?
9. Please describe what your organization has done well to encourage employees to speak up and share ideas. (RQ1)
- Probe 1 – Why did you say _____?
- Probe 2 – How could your organization become better?
10. Please describe the interpersonal relationship you have with your supervisor, your coworkers, and others in the organization. (RQ2)
- Probe 1 – How does your perception of your organizations psychological safety affect your interpersonal relationship within your workplace and team?
- Probe 2 – What do you think would happen if...?
11. Please describe how you feel when you voice your thoughts and feelings to your immediate supervisor. (RQ2)
- Probe 1 – How did you feel when your voice was welcomed? / How did you feel when your voice was unwelcomed?
- Probe 2 – What would you change to support your psychological safety?
12. Describe the influence that supervisor feedback may have on your psychological safety. (RQ2)
- Probe 1 – What type of supervisor feedback behaviors would make you feel unsafe? What type of supervisor feedback behaviors would make you feel safe?
- Probe 2 – What type of supervisor feedback behaviors do you feel allow an employee to freely express themselves?
13. Describe how your psychological safety in the organization has been affected by your supervisor. Explain. (RQ2)
- Probe 1 – Can you describe the influence your supervisor has on your level of work engagement?
- Probe 2 – Can you describe what your supervisor does great or not so great to support your psychological safety? How would you improve your supervisors influence and impact on your psychological safety?
14. Please describe your perception of the psychological safety impact on the quality of work within your organization. (RQ1/RQ2)

- Probe 1 – Why do you perceive the quality of work to be _____?
- Probe 2 – What policies and procedures do you feel have impact on the quality of work in your organization?
15. Please describe how supervisor influence on psychological safety has impacted your attitude and behavior within your organization. (RQ2)
- Probe 1 – Why do you feel that supervisor influence on psychological safety has impacted the _____ in your attitude and behavior at your workplace?
- Probe 2 – What aspects of leadership have contributed to your perception of the influence on your attitude and behavior?
- Probe 3 – What policies and practices have impacted your attitude and behavior that you described?
16. Please describe what your organization does well to address psychological safety within the workplace. (RQ1/RQ2)
- Probe 1 – What can your organization do more of to support psychological safety in your workplace?
17. Please describe what your supervisor does well to support positive psychological safety in the workplace. (RQ2)
- Probe 1 – What preventative measures could your supervisor include to increase the positive psychological safety in the workplace?
- Probe 2 – What aspects do you feel your supervisor could focus more on to increase psychological safety in the workplace?
18. Is there anything that you would like to add about your supervisor’s influence on your psychological safety that has not been discussed? Explain. (RQ2)

End Interview

1. Thank the respondent for their participation.
2. Inform the participant of the member checking process. Inform participant that the interview transcription will be emailed to them within 2-3 days of completion of the interview.
3. Inform participant that they will have 5 business days to confirm the accuracy of their interview transcription. Inform the participant that if nothing is received within 5 business days, the researcher will initiate a follow-up.
4. Ask participant if they have anyone that they can reach out to who might be interested in participating in the study and if so, have that person contact the researcher.

Research Questions

RQ1: How do federal government employees describe psychological safety in their workplace?

RQ2: How do federal government employees describe their supervisors' influence on psychological safety in their workplace?

References

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